

WORKPLACE INCIVILITY AND EMPLOYEES' PSYCHOLOGICAL STATUS AMONG STAFF OF LAGOS STATE MINISTRY HOME AFFAIRS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7516242>

Published Date: 09-January-2023

Abstract: The recent experiences of uncivil behaviours among members of organisations is calling for more indepth examination to despite the obvious effect of these uncivil behaviours to both individual and organisational outcomes the acts still remain a constant occurrence in the workplace. This study therefore examined the effects of workplace incivility on employees' psychological status among staff of Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs. The objective was to investigate the nature of relationship between vertical workplace incivility and employee's psychological status. The independent variable are vertical workplace incivility and horizontal workplace incivility while employee's psychological status anxiety and depression are dependent variables,. The research design utilized was the survey research design. The population of the study comprises of 164 employees working in the Ministry of Home Affairs. One hundred and fifteen respondents were selected as sample size, using the Krejcan and Morgan (1970) formula. Pearson Product correlation was used to test the two null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance computed within SPSS software. The study found that there is a positive and significant relationship between vertical workplace incivility and anxiety of employees. Also, there is significant relationship between horizontal workplace incivility and depression of employees as confirmed with the statistical results where the $r=0.758$, $P=0.00<0.05$ and $r=0.969$, $P=0.00<0.05$. The findings of this study support the need to appraise organizational incivility, especially among high-status employees, as perceived across all hierarchical levels considering the significant relationships between structure and workplace incivility and psychological health. The study concluded that workplace incivility is significantly associated with the measures of employee's psychological health and therefore recommend that organizations should attempt to foster a work environment where rude and discourteous behaviour is unacceptable. Managers should adopt informative training programmers for newly employed staff to set up a partnership between employees and employer that addresses individual desires. Managers should reexamine their hiring and selection procedures, selection criteria should include checking personality characteristics that could add buffering effect in dealing with a stressor at workplace. Management of organizations should deal with the causative factors of workplace incivility by way of strengthening ethical procedures, policies, effective communication plan, information infrastructures, good governance, direction and response so as to reduce workplace incivility to the barest minimum.

Keywords: Anxiety, Depression, Employees, Horizontal incivility, Psychological Status, Vertical incivility, Workplace incivility.

1. INTRODUCTION

Human by nature are very complex with a number of distinctive features. Humans are naturally multi-dimensional, and it means that people don't have only physical features but also psychological, cognitive and social skills. All these features complement one another and constitute the personality (Ozgur & Harika, 2019). According to Tsearenko, Leao, and Tse

(2018) when employees have good relations with their co-workers and supervisors as well as the work environment the use of recognition overrides the personal commitment benefits derived from the positive socialisation. Palmer, Niemand, Stockmann, Kraus, and Kailer (2017) used the term “psychological status” to point out that it includes different type of characteristics such as cognitive abilities, knowledge, and skills, personality tendencies, applied social skills and interests and preferences and that these status have much effects of work relationship and organisational outcomes.

Though in today’s present workplace the occurrence of incivility and relationship conflict in the workplace have been found to be a major factor affecting and influencing employees psychological status and workplace behaviours (Nicholson, Leiter, & Laschinger, 2014). However, uncivil acts between and among members of organisation are counterproductive to cultivating and sustaining effective working relationships, and are detrimental to employees psychological status in a number ways (Golonka & Mojsa-Kaja, 2013). Specifically, over time, repetitive acts of incivility disrupt teamwork, decrease worker productivity, and erode the quality of working relationships (Pearson & Porath, 2005). Incivility, manifest in form of bullying (Glendenning, 2001), psychological abuse, and mobbing (Davenport, Schwartz, & Elliott, 2002), in the workplace. It has been said to be so costly, widespread, and may be a precursor to workplace aggression and violence. Incivility has been reported to impact both individual and organisational performance (Wu, Zhang, Chiu, Kwan, & He, 2014). For example, Pearson and Porath (2005) noted that employees experiencing incivility at work intentionally reduced their work effort and spent work time telling coworkers about the incident and avoiding the instigator. Furthermore, it was reported that employees who suffered incivility considered quitting their jobs, and some did so to avoid the instigator (Golonka & Mojsa-Kaja, 2013).

Studies have clearly identified various adverse psychological effects of workplace incivility on those who experienced it, such as anxiety, confusion, depression, and even suicide (Golonka & Mojsa-Kaja, 2013; Nicholson, Leiter, & Laschinger, 2014; Pearson & Porath, 2005; Wu, Zhang, Chiu, Kwan, & He, 2014). As a result, workers experiencing incivility may engage in retaliation and sabotage (Nwaeke & Akani, 2019). Workplace incivility is confirmed to be inform of vertical incivility (top-down/down-top) or it can also be inform of horizontal incivility, that is, from members across the same level (Nwaeke & Akani, 2019; Gabriel & Akani, 2019). The fact that incivility results in significant negative impact on individuals and organisations demands serious attention (Pearson & Porath, 2004) from human resource scholars and practitioners.

According to Porath and Pearson (2013) incivility has to do with different degrees of uncivil human behaviours such as being rude, condescending, dismissive, or disrespectful behaviour. These uncivil behaviours can be in form of top-down, down-top or vertical. Vertical incivility in an organisation flows from either a lower-level employee to an upper level employee or vice versa while horizontal incivility flows among the employees at the same level in the organisation. Vertical incivility is becoming increasingly common with the flattening of organisational hierarchy and the advent of team work (Golonka & Mojsa-Kaja, 2013). Horizontal incivility in an organisation can serve for series of psychological effects such as failure of teamwork, depression, confusion among other (Nwaeke & Akani, 2019). There is need in contemporary times for organisations to pay serious attention to workplace incivility as competition intensifies and technology eliminates the traditional interactions among employees. The environment is becoming more sophisticated, constantly and swiftly changing. The job task is becoming very demanding as human resources are gradually replaced by machines; investors are requesting for results, employees are becoming more animated, stressed and crushed under the weight of targets and demands. These factors escalates incivility in the workplace, and the office environment is becoming more toxic and less best place to work contrary to claims of most organisations (Nwaeke & Akani, 2019).

Results of previous research have linked psychological status to a number of positive individual and organisational outcomes. For example, higher levels of psychological status have been linked to enhanced stress and anxiety management (Dong, Seo, Smith & Bartol, 2014; Johnson & Blanchard, 2016; Singh & Sharma, 2012; Ugogi, 2012). In addition, researchers have also shown that psychological status level is positively correlated with improved teamwork and productivity and negatively correlated with workplace deviance and counterproductive work behaviours (De Clercq, Bouckenoghe, Raja, & Matsyborska, 2014; Jung & Yoon, 2012).

Still others have demonstrated that psychological status contributes to heightened interpersonal sensitivity, greater ability to connect and communicate effectively with coworkers, and higher quality interpersonal relationships (Amudhadevi, 2012; Chhabra & Chhabra, 2013; Ng, Ke, & Raymond, 2014). While the benefits of psychological status in an organisational setting are well documented, studies evaluating the relationships between psychological status level and instigation of

workplace incivility have not been done. Therefore, a descriptive study was needed to investigate the relationships between individuals' level of psychological status level and their instigation of workplace incivility.

Statement of the Problem

Previous studies on workplace incivility have shown that incivility has negative outcomes on employees' work life and the organisational life, yet issues associated to workplace incivility escalates in organisations, this could be owing to lack of research on incivility and its effect on psychological status of organisational members. Although, there is seeming abundance of research on workplace incivility such as: Dong, Seo, Smith and Bartol, (2014); Johnson and Blanchard, (2016); Singh and Sharma, (2012); Ugogi, (2012), Porath and Pearson (2012) but the general focus has been on organisational and individual outcomes, this study however would be examining the relationship between incivility and psychological status of organisational members. It was also observed that most of the available studies as mentioned above do not conceptualize workplace incivility in its dimension using the horizontal and vertical dimensions, most of these studies have only consider workplace incivility as a single variables thereby leaving a conceptual gap which this study will be filling.

In the area of coverage, almost all the past studies have considered this workplace incivility in the private sector thereby leaving a paucity of investigation of the public sector especially in the Nigeria context, it is against this backdrop, that this study examined the effect of workplace incivility on psychological status of employees with a focus on Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs.

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of the study is to examine the relationship between workplace incivility and employees' psychological status. Specific objectives of the study are as follows:

- i. To examine the relationship between horizontal incivility and anxiety among employees' of Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs,
- ii. To investigate the relationship between vertical incivility and depression among employees' of Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs,

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the study objectives

- i. What is the relationship between horizontal incivility and anxiety among employees' of Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs?
- ii. What is the relationship between vertical incivility and depression among employees' of Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs?

Research Hypotheses

The study shall consider the following hypotheses in line with the study objectives:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between horizontal incivility and anxiety among employees of Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between vertical incivility and depression among employees of Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Workplace Incivility

Andersson and Pearson (1999) are the first to conceptualize workplace incivility, they defined it as "low intensity deviant behaviour with ambiguous intent to harm the target, in violation of workplace norms for mutual respect". Incivility includes a variety of workplace behaviours that can seriously undermine trust and mutual respect between individuals (Blau & Andersson, 2005). Specifically, incivility is rude, condescending, dismissive, or disrespectful behaviour directed at one or more colleagues (Porath & Pearson, 2013). Common manifestations of incivility include verbally or nonverbally

discrediting a colleague, directing disparaging remarks toward a colleague, dismissing or disregarding a colleague's actions or decisions, or excluding a colleague from key business activities (Porath & Pearson, 2013). Undermining trust and mutual respect between and among colleagues is one of the more serious consequences of incivility because it has the potential to erode existing cordial working relationships and make it much more difficult to establish and maintain collaborative working relationships going forward (Li & Tan, 2013).

Given the potential detrimental consequences of workplace incivility, the following behaviours in the workplace are considered as contributing to workplace incivility; It is rude or disrespectful behaviour that demonstrates a lack of regard for other employees, although it may be obvious, it's often hidden, subtle, or only obvious in hindsight (Porath & Pearson, 2013). The intent to harm, as perceived by the instigator, the target, or an observer, is often ambiguous or difficult to pin down or articulate giving rise to conflicting reactions. Incivility is sometimes intentional, but sometimes it is just plain thoughtlessness or insensitivity towards others (Sakurai & Jex, 2012).

Even small indignities (such as playing music aloud in the open office, changing the room temperature without asking, or not refilling the office refrigerator after consumed) and minor cruelties (such as snubbing a co-worker or not inviting someone to a function when everyone else has been invited) take a toll on all employees - managers and workers alike. They add to the burden of stress and fatigue that is already present in the workplace and they have real consequences on the everyday lives of people. This is especially true when incivilities involve a fundamental lack of respect, such as eavesdropping, being loud, not acknowledging colleagues in the hallway, and gossiping" (Sakurai & Jex, 2012). Other examples of workplace incivility according to (Sakurai & Jex, 2012) includes, "Forgetting" to share credit for collaborative work, always taking credit; never taking blame, asking for input and opinion and then discounting or ignoring it, hindering access to information for others who need it to do their job; over-ruling decisions and not providing rationale, information, or justification, failure to attempt or build consensus when needed among others

According to Golonka and Mojsa-Kaja (2013), uncivil behaviours in the workplace is commonly seen in two forms which are top-down or down-top (vertical incivility) and also line-line (horizontal incivility).

Horizontal Incivility

Horizontal informal communication flows among the employees at the same level in the organisation. In today's organisation, horizontal communication is becoming increasingly common with the flattening of organisational hierarchy and the advent of team work (Singh & Sharma, 2012; Ugogi, 2012). Offensive, abusive, intimidating, malicious or insulting behaviour, or abuse of power, usually perpetrated by an individual or group against others of the same hierarchical level, which makes the recipient feel upset, depressed, humiliated or vulnerable, confuse and undermines their self-confidence and which may cause them to suffer stress. Horizontal incivility and horizontal hostility can be manifested in verbal or nonverbal behaviors. The ten most common forms of horizontal violence among employees are: non-verbal innuendo, verbal affront, undermining activities, withholding information, sabotage, infighting, backstabbing, failure to respect privacy, and broken confidences (Griffin, 2004). This includes disruptive behaviour, a kind of behaviour that interferes with effective work relationship among employees and negatively impacts performance and outcomes.

Vertical Incivility

Upward/downward informal communication in an organisation flows from a lower-level employee to an upper-level employee and vice versa. Upward communication is used to keep managers informed of what is going on in the work and what the subordinates are feeling. Specifically, it provides management with the information they need for doing their work, such as data for making decisions, the current status of projects, and information on new problems. Incivility is considered down top if they were reported as being perpetrated by subordinate to superior. Workplace incivility has also been found to be common in supervisor and subordinate relationships (Sakurai & Jex, 2012). Down top incivility manifests in many ways in the work relationship between subordinate and supervisor, Pearson and Porath (2009) found that incivility that starts from the bottom of the organisational hierarchy and directs upwards is exerted in other ways than incivility exerted in the opposite direction, employees can use passive- aggressive methods to sabotage supervisor and to undercut his or her power. Such as employee silence,

On the other hand, Incivility is considered top-down if they were reported as being perpetrated by superior to subordinate (Sakurai & Jex, 2012). Top-down incivility manifests in many ways in the work relationship from superior to subordinate, Pearson and Porath (2009) found that incivility such verbal abuse, ignoring, not crediting good work, unfair distribution of resources among others constitutes top-down incivility.

Psychological Status

On the other hand, the term of psychology as the mental or behavioral characteristics of an individual or group meets the status business especially in the analysis phase. Status analyst's mental abilities carry responsibilities while he/she is assessing and evaluating given evidences (Vishnupriya & Sakthipriya, 2013). Workplace psychology is the study of day-to-day individual and collective human behaviour in organisations and the workplace to understand how work behavior can be influenced, changed, and/or improved to benefit both employees & organisations. Workplace psychology sometimes is concerned with understanding, explaining, and ultimately improving the attitudes and behaviors of individuals and groups in organisations and applying this knowledge to problems at work (Vishnupriya & Sakthipriya, 2013).

Understanding an employee by his/her emotion, thoughts, behavior, and physical conditions as a whole are important for improvement of conditions. Considering only the physical condition wouldn't improve the efficiency of the employees. For that reason, physical and psychological conditions of employees need to be taken into account (Ruck, Welch & Menera, 2017). Psychological status plays an important role on increasing employee's productivity as well as efficiency. There are literally many different definitions for psychological status it is the capability of a balanced and harmonized relationship with others, to change and reform social and individual milieu, to resolve personal contrasts and tendencies rationally, fairly and properly (Porath & Pearson, 2013)..

According to Leiter, and Laschinger (2014), psychological status related to work attitudes and engagement are associated with performance. They also noted that people with higher psychological status at work are healthier (both mentally and physically), have happier lives and live longer. There is clear evidence that between psychological status and performance positively related. In their study, they also proved that "there are statistically significant relationships between scores on the survey and business unit level outcomes, including customer satisfaction, productivity, profitability, employee turnover and sickness/absence level. They discussed that employees with higher psychological status appear to behave differently than others and they show better psychological well-being bases such as optimism, resilientness, and a strong feeling of ability to cope with challenges. However, according to Salovey and Mayer (1990), psychologically individuals have a greater ability to perceive, understand, and appropriately interpret a variety of emotions encountered in self and others in daily interactions, and an ability to use psychological information for effective interpersonal interaction. Similarly, Goleman (2006) conceptualized psychological and social status as the ability to assess and use a variety of non-cognitive cues and information for effective social interaction. Different form of psychological effects among organisational members have been identified in various studies to include anxiety, confusion, depression, and even suicide (Golonka & Mojsa-Kaja, 2013; Nicholson, Leiter, & Laschinger, 2014; Pearson & Porath, 2005; Wu, Zhang, Chiu, Kwan, & He, 2014).

Anxiety: Not everyone is able to effectively manage and cope with their anxiety at work. Many people struggle with excessive worry about a variety of everyday problems related to work or their personal lives while trying to get their job done (Pearson & Porath, 2005). Workplace anxiety involves feeling stressed, nervous, uneasy, or tense about work, which could include anxiety about job performance, interactions with co-workers, or work demands (Goleman, 2006). Having anxiety at work can have a huge impact employees' career. People who feel anxious at work might even make negative career decisions based on their anxiety (Golonka & Mojsa-Kaja, 2013).

Depression: According to Leiter, and Laschinger (2014) there are so many factors that can cause depression at work, these include the work demand, workplace relationship, organizational politics and hostility within the work environment. Any workplace situation or job can be a potential cause or a contributing factor for depression depending on the level of stress and available support at the workplace (Goleman, 2006). Depression is a complex issue and many individuals who experience it can feel different symptoms at different times. The most common signs of depression are a lack of energy, low mood, decreased focus, feeling worthless, empty, and helpless and generally not being able to find pleasure in the things you love (Singh & Sharma, 2012).

Psychology status and workplace incivilities

Psychological status here is defined as feeling able to show and employ one's self without fear of negative consequences to self-image, status, or career (Sakurai & Jex, 2012). Sakurai and Jex (2012) further argued that supervisory and co-worker behaviors who are supportive and trustworthy in nature are likely to produce feelings of safety at work. Research also showed that leadership style is an important antecedent to psychological safety (Duan, 2012). That is, supervisor's behaviors have stronger relationship with psychological safety. Empirical studies have found that abusive supervision has negative relationship with psychological safety (Wu et al., 2014). Wu et al (2014) also pointed out that incivility breaks the norm of mutual respect and, hence, evokes feelings of injustice in the target. Furthermore, uncivil behavior signals that one is not valued and accepted by the other, which threatens one's social standing and self-esteem (Duan, 2012), thus, decreasing employee's psychology safety in the workplace.

Therefore, when incivility occur in the workplace it turns out to be a stressor on employees and then create some psychological imbalance. After which, employees would be acting negatively to both superior and colleagues. Empirical studies (Golonka & Mojsa-Kaja, 2013; Nicholson, Leiter, & Laschinger, 2014; Pearson & Porath, 2005; Wu, Zhang, Chiu, Kwan, & He, 2014) have found that psychology status has positive relationship with employee's retention, but has negative relationship with employee's silence and turnover intention (He, 2010). That is, psychology status is a significant antecedent for employee's behaviour. Therefore, faced with incivility, employees make a cognition appraisal and take it as potential pressure, thereby threatening self-esteem, ultimately reducing psychological safety and further increasing employee's negative work behaviours.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1: Relationship between workplace incivility and Employees Psychological Status

Source: Author's Conceptualisation (2021)

Theoretical Framework: Social exchange theory

This study is anchored on Social Exchange Theory which evolved from Thorndike's work of (1935) on the development of Reinforcement Theory. The model comprise of five central elements which are behaviour, relationship, social exchange, individual gains and participation:

Behaviour is predicated upon the notion of rationality: That is, the more behaviour results in a reward, the more individuals will behave that way and expect to enjoy many of such rewards.

Relationship is based on reciprocity: That is, each individual in the relationship will provide a reaction to the other so long as the exchange is equitable and the units of exchange are important to the respective parties. An exchange between two individuals must be seen as fair by both parties for the relationship to thrive.

Social exchange is based on a justice principle: In each exchange, there should be a norm of fairness governing behaviour. The exchange must be viewed as fair when compared in the context of a wider network to third and fourth parties. This notion of distributive justice goes beyond the equity between the two principals' contribution. It involves each person comparing his or her reward to that of others who have dealt with this individual (the employee's superior) and what they received for the same or a similar contribution.

Individual gains, individuals will seek to maximize their gains and minimize their costs in the exchange relationship: It is important to understand that the notion of costs does not relate exclusively to financial issues; rather, costs can be incurred through outcomes of uncivil attitudes.

Individuals participate in a relationship out of a sense of mutual benefit rather than coercion. Thus, coercion should be minimized as employees tend to view the work sphere as fair and just in cases where social ties can support their interests and ambitions.

This theory is relevant to this study because the five central elements of the theory reflect the incivility behaviours and relationship that are displayed among members of organisation. Because the workplace environment is a replica of the society where human relationship is characterized with various form of power tussle of social interest hence, the occurrence of uncivil behaviours. In like manner, the workplace also comprised of human element who fights for shared resource and corporate benefits and in the course of this the likelihood of uncivil behaviour is possibly experienced.

3. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Vertical Incivility and Employee Psychological Status

Chang and Lyons (2012) found that uncivil behavior of coworkers had a direct impact on turnover intention whereas uncivil behavior from other work-related persons such as supervisors, customers had an indirect effect on turnover intention, mediated through emotional strain. Farzana and Qasim (2016) in their study found that workplace incivility produces job stress and lead to employee absent from work. Workplace civility is an imperative role associated with positive workforce behavior that makes firm output efficient.

Pearson, Andersson, and Wegner (2001) conducted a study that involved the use of qualitative methods aimed at identifying the nature of workplace and how it affects employees and organisations. They found that employees who experienced workplace incivility described their feelings of negative states such as depressed, down, irritable, hurt, scared and angry. Furthermore, some employees wanted to get back at the coworkers by treating them in the same way they thought they were treated. Lastly, employees reported that they avoided uncivil coworkers or work altogether, by showing up late and leaving early, or just by taking unnecessary days off from work.

Horizontal Incivility and Employee Psychological Status

Daniel and Eze (2016) examined the extent to which formal and informal communication relates with affective and continuance commitment in Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC), Nigerian Agip Oil Company (NAOC) and Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG). Taro Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size of 400 of which 323 copies of questionnaire were retrieved and 271 copies were useful for analyses. The study found significant relationship existing between formal communication, affective commitment and continuance commitment. There was a significant relationship that existing between informal communication, affective commitment and continuance commitment.

Ergen (2010) attempted to bring forth, analyze and compare different aspects in terms of workplace communication. It focuses in the informal communication which considered a significant factor for an organisation's internal and external progress. It is a study on literature, which aims to link the literature findings with a real case of a company which seeks to improve its workplace communication. In the end, it proposes certain strategies to be followed in order to control and affect the existed informal communications network. Thus, cultivation of communities of practice and face-to face contacts is expected to influence and turn the informal network to an added-value for the organisation.

Similarly, Ottinot (2008) findings provided evidence that workplace incivility climate relates to the occurrence of prevalent low intensity aggressive behaviors. The study also found that workplace incivility climate is shared among coworkers. Hershcovis and Barling (2010) provided evidence for differential effects of source and workplace aggression by meta-analytically comparing the outcomes of aggression from different perpetrators. Results showed that supervisor aggression had stronger negative relations than co-worker aggression on numerous variables including job satisfaction, affective organisational commitment, turnover intentions, general health, and performance.

Miner Settles, Pratt-Hyatt, and Brady (2012) tested whether social support could protect employees from the stress brought on by experiencing workplace incivility. They argued that social support can help employees either by altering the way in which they perceive or appraise the experience of incivility in the first place or by mitigating the negative effects of the incivility experience. The negative effects of incivility can be mitigated on an emotional level whereby employees receive comfort and encouragement from friends, family, or co-workers or they can receive support on an organisational level which shows individuals that their organisation cares about them.

4. METHODOLOGY

This study employed the survey research method because this method allows a researcher to freely investigate an event in a selected population through most likely primary method. It made use of questionnaire as a means of gathering useful and accurate data relating to the topic under study. The population of the study comprised of staff of Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs, Lagos State, Nigeria. Available reports show that the staff population of the Lagos State Ministries of Home Affairs is 164 staff as provided by the ministry personnel records.

Table 1: Staff Spread in Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs (2021)

Categories	Male	Female	Total
Management staff	8	4	12
Senior Staff	36	38	74
Junior Staff	32	46	78
Total	76	88	164

Source: Records office; Ministry of Home Affairs, Alausa Ikeja (March, 2022)

The study adopts the simple random sampling technique. The simple random sample is a subset of a statistical population in which each member of the subset has an equal probability of being chosen. A simple random sample is meant to be an unbiased representation of a group, therefore the method was used to select the sample size of one hundred and fifteen (115) from the population which was determine with Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination table.

The primary data were obtained through the administration of questionnaire to the respondents. The hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation with the aid of (SPSS) computer software for the analysis. The face validity which is a type of content validity test was adopted, which depends on researcher's subjective evaluation as the validity of a measuring instrument.

Self-administered questionnaire was used as an instrument to capture the perceptions of respondents regarding workplace incivility and employee psychological status. Items related to workplace incivility (10 items) were adapted from the scale of Gabriel and Akani (2019) the first five measure horizontal factors of workplace incivility and the last five items measures vertical factors; while employee psychological status (10 items) were taken from the scale of Johnson (2003). To check the accuracy and consistency of the instrument Cronbach alpha was used for test calculation. The Cronbach alpha value 0.79 was arrived at, indicating the suitability of the questionnaire. Further data analysis was carried out using Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

5. RESULT OF DATA ANALYSIS

From the one hundred and fifteen (115) copies of the questionnaires administered to the respondents from the selected ministry, the researcher was able to retrieve eighty-six (86) copies which is about 75% of the instruments which were now used for the analysis as shown below:

Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses stated earlier are empirically tested using the responses from the research instrument administered.

Hypothesis One:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between horizontal incivility and anxiety among employees of Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs.

Table 2: Correlation analysis of Hypothesis One

		Horizontal Incivility	Anxiety
Horizontal Incivility	Pearson Correlation	1	.758**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	86	86
Anxiety	Pearson Correlation	.758**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	86	86

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The analysis from the correlation table above shows that the p-value < 0.01 (at a 2-tailed test). This means that the result is statistically significant at 1% confidence level. The r value 0.758 (76%) shows that there is a strong positive relationship between horizontal incivility and anxiety of employee in Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs

Hypothesis Two:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between vertical incivility and depression among employees of Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs

Table 3: Correlation analysis of Hypothesis Two

		Vertical Incivility	Employee Depression
Vertical Incivility	Pearson Correlation	1	.969**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	86	86
Employee Depression	Pearson Correlation	.969**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	86	86

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table above shows that p-value < 0.01 (at a 2-tailed test). This means that the result is statistically significant at 1% confidence level. The r value 0.969 (97%) shows that there is a very strong positive relationship between vertical incivility and employees' depression in Lagos State Ministry Home Affairs.

6. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Relationship between Horizontal Incivility and Anxiety

Findings from the study reveal that there is significant correlation coefficient between horizontal workplace incivility and anxiety among employees of the Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs. The correlation result shows that the p-value < 0.01 (at a 2-tailed test). This means that the result is statistically significant at 1% confidence level. The r value 0.758 (76%) shows that there is a strong positive relationship between horizontal incivility and anxiety of employee in Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs. The findings of the study show that the null hypothesis is rejected. The implication of this study is that presence of horizontal workplace incivility will significantly affect the psychological state of employees of the ministry in Lagos State. The finding is in conformity with our a-priori expectation of the result and validates the opinion of Saira (2016) who opined that workplace incivility is evidenced in behaviour that demonstrate lack of regard for others in the workplace, behaviours that are described as rude or discourteous. It also support the opinion of Meier and Gross (2015) who noted that workplace incivility is deviant workplace behaviour with ambiguous interest to harm the target low level employees in violation of workplace norms and mutual respect.

Relationship between Vertical Workplace Incivility and Employee Depression

The second hypothesis revealed that there is significant relationship between vertical workplace incivility and depression (employee health) among employees of the Home Affairs Ministry in Lagos State. The correlation coefficient was to test the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variable. The findings revealed that that p-value < 0.01 (at a 2 tailed test). This means that the result is statistically significant at 1% confidence level. The r value 0.969 (97%) shows that there is a very strong positive relationship between vertical incivility and employees' depression in Lagos State Ministry Home Affairs.

The finding confirms the a-priori expectation of the study and empirical finding of other scholars such as the findings of Kibe (2014) on the significant relationship between vertical communication strategies and organisational performance. The finding also conform with the opinion of Saira (2016) that existence of work place incivility has a negative impact on organisational and employees health. The finding further agrees to the finding of Kibe (2014) on the negative impact of vertical communication on organisational performance.

7. CONCLUSION

In view of the findings from the study, it was then concluded that workplace incivility is very significant with the measures of employees psychological status in Lagos State Ministry of Home Affairs, this study further conclude that there are traces of workplace incivility in the ministry as a result of uncivil work relationship been put up by both down and top level employees. The above conclusions contribute to the existing body of knowledge on the relationship between incivility and employee psychological status in three areas; it has help you to develop the existing literature thereby assessing current developments in studies which address the relationship between variables and incorporating this research studies into a general framework which would assist researchers and practitioners of the changes in the studies relating to issues of incivility and organisational outcomes. This study has established the fact that workplace incivility has become chronic in Lagos State public sector but can be well control with the application of the study findings and lastly, the study conclude that based on the findings, organisations will be more aware and better prepared and positioned to bring out the desirable performance from their employees.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are premised on the evidence presented by the findings of the study and the conclusions drawn thereof. They are as follows:

- i. Organisations should attempt to foster a work environment and climate where rude and discourteous behaviour is unacceptable. There should be risk Management model of workplace civility where organisations try to reflect that incivility at work makes for a hazardous social environment. By promoting civility at work, organisations can improve both organisational outcomes and the quality of workplace relationships.
- ii. Mangers should adopt informative training programmers for newly employed staff to set up a partnership between employee and employer that addresses individual desires. To contain the costs of incivility, incidents should be curtailed and corrected when they occur, regardless of the status of the instigator.
- iii. Managers should reexamine their hiring and selection procedures, selection criteria should include checking personality characteristics that could add buffering effect in dealing with a stressor at workplace. Findings from this research have important implications for personnel management.
- iv. Management of organisations should deal with the causative factors of workplace incivility by way of strengthening ethical procedures, policies, effective communication plan, information infrastructures, good governance, direction and response so as to reduce workplace incivility to the barest minimum.

REFERENCES

- [1] Amudhadevi, N. V. (2012). A study on emotional status in relation to interpersonal relationship and role stress among school teachers. *Indian Journal of Positive Psychology*, 3(3), 330-332.
- [2] Andersson, L. M., & Pearson, C. M. (1999). Tit for Tat? The spiraling effect of incivility in the workplace. *Academy of Management Review*, 24(3), 452-471.

- [3] Blau, G. & Andersson, L. (2005), Testing a measure of instigated workplace incivility”, *Journal of Occupational and Organisational Psychology*, 78, 595-614.
- [4] Chhabra, M., & Chhabra, B. (2013). Emotional status and occupational stress: a study of Indian Border Security Force personnel. *Police Practice and Research*, 14(5), 355–370.
- [5] Cortina, L. M., Magley, V. J., Williams, J. H., & Langhout, R. D. (2001). Incivility in the workplace: incidence and impact. *Journal of occupational health psychology*, 6(1), 64.
- [6] Davenport, N. D., Schwartz, R. D., & Elliott, G. P. (2002). *Mobbing: Emotional abuse in the American workplace*. Ashland, OH: BookMasters.
- [7] De Clercq, D., Bouckennooghe, D., Raja, U., & Matsyorskya, G. (2014). Unpacking the goal congruence–organisational deviance relationship: The roles of work engagement and emotional status. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 124(4), 695–711
- [8] Dong, Y., Seo, M-G., Smith, R. H., & Bartol, K. M. (2014). No pain, no gain: An affectbased model of developmental job experience and the buffering effects of emotional status. *Academy of Management Journal*, 57(4), 1056–1077.
- [9] Duan, J. Y.(2012). The influence of paternalistic leadership on employee voice behavior: mediated by psychological safety. *Management Review*. 24(10).109-116
- [10] Gabriel, J.M.O. & Akani, V. C. (2019) Vertical workplace incivility and organisational health of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Human Resource Management*, 7 (3), 15-39,
- [11] Gawali, K. C. (2012). Relationship between emotional status and coping among college teachers. *Journal of Psychosocial Research*, 7(1), 25-32.
- [12] Goleman, D. (2006). *Social Status*. New York, NY: Bantam Dell. 132
- [13] Golonka, K., & Mojsa-Kaja, J. (2013). Emotional status and team roles: Analysis of interdependencies with regard to team work effectiveness. *International Journal of Contemporary Management*, 12(4), 32-44. 8723.
- [14] Griffin, B. (2010). Multilevel relationships between organisational-level incivility, justice and intention to stay. *Work & Stress*, 24(4), 309-323.
- [15] Johnson, S. K., & Blanchard, A. (2016). Emotional status and mental health: Stress and symptom reporting pathways. *Journal of Mental Health Counseling*, 38(1), 79-92.
- [16] Jung, H. S., & Yoon, H. H. (2012). The effects of emotional status on counterproductive work behaviors and organisational citizen behaviors among food and beverage employees in a deluxe hotel. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 31(2), 369– 378
- [17] Li, A. N., & Tan, H. H. (2013). What happens when you trust your supervisor? Mediators of individual performance in trust relationships. *Journal of Organisational Behavior*, 34(3), 407–425.
- [18] Meier, L. L., Gross, S., Spector, P. E., & Semmer, N. K. (2013). Relationship and task conflict at work: Interactive short-term effects on angry mood and somatic complaints. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 18(2), 144–156.
- [19] Ng, S., M., Ke, G. N., & Raymond, W. (2014). The mediating role of work locus of control on the relationship among emotional status, organisational citizenship behaviours, and mental health among nurses. *Australian Journal of Psychology*; 66(4), 207–215
- [20] Nicholson, R. M., Leiter, M. P., & Laschinger, H. K. (2014). Predicting cynicism as a function of trust and civility: A longitudinal analysis. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 22(8), 974–983.
- [21] Nwaeke, L.I. & Akani, V. C, (2019), Down top workplace incivility and organisational health of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management*. 7(5),.61-84,
- [22] Ozgur D. & Harika S. (2019), Employees’ Psychological Performance. *Human Resource Research*. 3 (1), 13-23

- [23] Pearson, C. M., & Porath, C. L. (2005). On the nature, consequences and remedies of workplace incivility: No time for “nice”? Think again. *Academy of Management Executive*, 19 (1), 7-18
- [24] Pearson, C. M., & Porath, C. L. (2009). *The cost of bad behavior: How incivility damages your business and what you can do about it*. New York: Portfolio
- [25] Pearson, C. M., Andersson, L. M., & Wegner, J. (2001). When workers flout convention: A study of workplace incivility. *Human Relations*, 54(11), 1387-1419.
- [26] Porath, C. L., & Pearson, C. M. (2013). Emotional and behavioral responses to workplace incivility and the impact of hierarchical status. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 42(1), 326–357
- [27] Ruck, K., Welch, M., & Menera, B. (2017). Employee voice: An antecedent to organisational engagement? *Public Relations Review*, 43, 904-914.
- [28] Sakurai, K., & Jex, S. M. (2012). Coworker incivility and incivility targets’ work effort and counterproductive work behaviors: The moderating role of supervisor social support. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 17(2), 150–161.
- [29] Salovey, P., & Mayer, J. D. (1990). Emotional status. *Imagination, Cognition and Personality*, 9(3), 185-211. Retrieved from us.sagepub.com/enus/nam/imagination-cognition-and-personality/journal20239
- [30] Singh, Y., & Sharma, R. (2012). Relationship between general status, emotional status, stress levels and stress reactivity. *Annals of Neurosciences*, 19(3), 107-111
- [31] Tsarenkoa, Y., Leob, C., & Herman, H. M. T. (2018). When and why do social resources influence employee advocacy? The role of personal investment and perceived recognition. *Journal of Business Research*, 82, 260-268.
- [32] Ugogi, N. (2012). Perceived emotional status and stress management among undergraduate students. *Ife Psychologia*, 20(2), 102-106.
- [33] Vishnupriya, K., & Sakthipriya, R. (2013). Informing successful teamwork through social and emotional competencies. *International Journal of Trade & Global Business Perspectives*, 2(1), 263-265
- [34] Wu, L. Z., Zhang, H., Chiu, R. K., Kwan, H. K., & He, X. (2014). Hostile attribution bias and negative reciprocity beliefs exacerbate incivility’s effects on interpersonal deviance. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 120(2), 189-199